

Association of Epstein - Barr Virus (EBV) in Breast Cancer Patients of North-East India

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Purpose of Study : Epstein - Barr virus (EBV) has been found to be associated with nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC). EBV has also been associated with breast carcinoma (BC) as one of its risk factors. In the current study, the presence of EBNA1 gene product of EBV is detected in breast cancer patients.

Methods : The study was conducted among 53 breast cancer patients. The DNA was isolated from the BC patient's peripheral blood. For the detection of EBNA1 gene of EBV, standard Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) was done.

Results : 20.8% (11 of 53 BC patient samples) showed the presence of EBNA1 gene. The mean age of BC patients were 42.87 years. 96.22% were diagnosed with high grade malignancy. 54.54% of EBV positive BC patients were diagnosed with T3 and T4 stage cancer. A significant association (p value: **0.056**, OR: 0.836) of AR positivity in EBV positive patients was observed as well.

Conclusion : From the current study, a potential association of EBV and BC can be established. Although considerable evidence has been found, the exact nature of EBV's etiology in BC is not confirmed. Hence, further investigative studies are required to conclusively establish the role of EBV and BC.

Keywords: EBV, Epstein-Barr, virus, breast cancer, PCR.